

EOSC POLICY BRIEF

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-06

PROJECT: EOSC4CANCER, A European-wide foundation to accelerate Data-driven Cancer Research

PROJECT WEB SITE: www.eosc4cancer.eu

GRANT NUMBER: 101058427

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SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief enables EU-funded projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to report on progress and provide input for further policy analysis and development by the European Commission. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the [European Research Area](#) (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the [ERA policy agenda](#) (in particular ERA action 1 & 8). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association.

The [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA) co-developed with the entire EOSC community sets 3 General Objectives (GO), 14 Operational Objectives (OO) and 14 Action Areas (AA).

General Objectives (GO):

1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.
2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.
3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

Operational Objectives (OO):

1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;
2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);
3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;
4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;

5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);
6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;
7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;
8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership.
9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership.
10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.

<u>Action Areas (AA) of a technical nature:</u>	<u>Action Areas (AA) related to boundary conditions:</u>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifiers 2. Metadata and ontologies 3. FAIR metrics and certification 4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure 5. User environments 6. Resource provider environments 7. EOSC Interoperability Framework 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Rules of Participation 9. Landscape monitoring 10. Business models 11. Skills and training 12. Rewards and recognition 13. Communication 14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global

More information can be found from:

- https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>
- <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about>

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 6P)

- A. Overview of contributions in relation to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives. Please briefly describe the main contributions of the project so far in relation to the General Objectives (GO) of the EOSC SRIA. As far as possible, please indicate the relation between each contribution and the most relevant Operational Objective(s) (OO) and Action Area(s) (AA) of the EOSC SRIA.

Example: AA3 - OO7 - OO13: Project contribution ... Link to deliverable (if applicable)
 (Further information and context can be found in sections 5, 6 and 8 of the [SRIA](#))

AA User Environment and AA Resource Provider Environments

EOSC4Cancer has made significant progress in the development and integration of virtual research environments (VREs), which serve as key enablers for data analysis, visualization, and knowledge extraction

in cancer research. These environments ensure secure, efficient, and interoperable access to cancer-related data and analytical workflows.

Two major platforms underpin these efforts: Galaxy and OpenVRE, both widely adopted in the Life Sciences domain. These systems offer user-friendly environments for running complex bioinformatics workflows and are already operational across diverse research projects and communities. In EOSC4Cancer, they have been tailored to support accessible, interoperable, and reproducible analytical workflows specifically relevant to cancer research, contributing to the standardization and harmonization of data, connection to tools and pipelines, and enhanced reproducibility of results.

To address the visualization and interpretation of complex cancer datasets, EOSC4Cancer also integrates cBioPortal, an open-source platform designed for interactive exploration of cancer genomics data in conjunction with clinical and longitudinal information. This environment supports longitudinal analyses along the patient journey, from prevention and first diagnosis to advanced disease stages, allowing researchers to contextualize genomic changes over time.

EOSC4Cancer has demonstrated the power of interconnecting analysis systems with data repositories and visualization tools through several technical demonstrators:

- Nextcloud-Galaxy-cBioPortal: This workflow illustrates the seamless transfer of raw sequencing data from Nextcloud to Galaxy for processing (e.g., alignment, annotation, generation of VCF and MAF files), and the subsequent import into cBioPortal for interactive exploration. This setup exemplifies the complete data flow, from raw data to actionable insight, while supporting reproducibility, scalability, and compliance with FAIR principles.
- EGA–OpenVRE–cBioPortal: Building on the existing linkage between EGA and OpenVRE, this prototype enables secure analysis of sensitive data within OpenVRE, followed by automated transfer of results to user-specific cBioPortal instances for visualization. This pipeline demonstrates data usage in a privacy-aware context, allowing researchers to analyze sensitive data without moving it from secure environments, and illustrates how integrated tools can facilitate intuitive interpretation of complex datasets.
- cBioPortal-Galaxy-cBioportal for longitudinal genomic data: EOSC4Cancer has developed novel functionalities that enhance interoperability and reuse. For example, cBioPortal is now capable of triggering external workflows, such as those in Galaxy, with results automatically pushed back into the portal. This was piloted using longitudinal mutation data analyzed via PyClone VI, enabling longitudinal clonal tracking and dynamic tumor profiling, all visualized within a single integrated environment.
- cBioPortal-Galaxy-cBioportal for imaging data: EOSC4Cancer has incorporated medical imaging capabilities into cBioPortal, embedding viewers for whole slide histopathology and radiology images. This integration allows users to intuitively navigate genomic, clinical, and imaging data within the same platform. Building on these foundations, new functionality has been developed to trigger imaging analysis workflows directly from cBioPortal, again leveraging Galaxy. This enables not only visualization but also in situ analysis of medical images, with the resulting outputs rendered alongside the original images in cBioPortal. Together, these features provide a versatile, federated environment for cancer researchers, bridging omics, clinical, and imaging data into a unified, FAIR-compliant research tool.

EOSC4Cancer focuses on the use and reuse of FAIR cancer-related data from distributed repositories. Interoperability is grounded in FAIR standards, not only for data but also for research software and workflows. The project contributes protocols and procedures to support FAIR adoption, including for sensitive data, where ensuring FAIRness without direct access poses unique challenges. Special attention is also given to enhancing the FAIRness and quality of digital research tools, reinforcing reproducibility and reusability.

Beyond these systems and the duration of the project, EOSC4Cancer has worked on a roadmap to outline the Cancer Data Infrastructure. On top of that, it takes into account the input from patient organisations as well as the roadmaps of the European Cancer landscape: EU Cancer Mission, EOSC projects and other initiatives with

a component of data management and analysis. The roadmap has been validated in consultation with various key stakeholders in and outside of EOSC4Cancer, including communities in EU Cancer Mission, cancer research, data initiatives, and EOSC. It is important to highlight that such roadmap is done in conjunction with different EU Research infrastructures such as ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN and EuroBioimaging as it is expected that they would contribute to the long-term sustainability and alignment with the various on-going projects and others to come.

AA Metadata and ontologies

Achieving interoperability in cancer research relies heavily on accurate metadata descriptions and the use of shared ontologies and data models to ensure data can be effectively reused. In EOSC4Cancer, we address this challenge by developing and promoting recommendations, guidelines, and standard operating procedures (SOPs) for structuring and describing cancer-related data.

Our approach is grounded in the use of common data models, widely adopted controlled vocabularies, and ontologies. This includes attention to how data and metadata are modeled before capture, ensuring consistency across the data lifecycle. While the recommendations are applicable across oncology, examples from metastatic colorectal cancer datasets are used to illustrate key points.

EOSC4Cancer also builds upon existing best practices from initiatives such as AACR GENIE, the BIMG minimal dataset for cancer, and data from comprehensive cancer centers. In collaboration with projects like HealthData@EU, we explore how to make clinical data, originally collected for patient care, interoperable and reusable for research, in line with the European Health Data Space (EHDS). These best practices are continuously shared with the EOSC4Cancer community to promote awareness and adoption.

Within the project, we apply these principles to a wide range of use cases that follow the patient journey laying the groundwork for robust data workflows in future Cancer Mission initiatives. A key activity has been the formulation of SOPs per data type, which guide data access, modeling, and interoperability.

In parallel, we have worked on a harmonized model for colorectal cancer (CRC) screening programs across Europe. Despite the richness of data, current CRC screening programs vary greatly, making integration and secondary use difficult. Starting from four real-world in-house data models, we developed a common data model to serve as a foundation for interoperable screening data. This effort is part of a broader aim to FAIRify cancer screening data, and a manuscript on this work is currently in preparation.

AA Skills and training

Throughout the EOSC4Cancer project, there have been substantial contributions to advancing the skills and training landscape for cancer data research in alignment with the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) objectives, with members of the consortium as active contributors in the EOSC-A Expert Opportunity Area 5 “Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling”. The EOSC4Cancer training portfolio for cancer research provides resources, skills, and training to biomedical researchers, healthcare professionals, and others in the field so they are exposed to the use of diverse data types together with different tools and elements developed by EOSC4Cancer.

This portfolio, accessible via the dedicated Cancer Data View page in the ELIXIR RDMkit, consolidates good practices in cancer data management, structured around the patient journey, and integrates a curated catalogue of existing and new courses on cancer research data. The RDMkit Cancer View serves as a central resource for both trainers and self-learners, supporting the development of essential competencies in data collection, integration, analysis, visualization, and long-term data stewardship, all underpinned by FAIR principles and the ELIXIR training structure.

Another key achievement was the systematic mapping of skills and roles within the cancer research data ecosystem, resulting in a skills matrix that informs the design of targeted curricula and learning paths. This

mapping, developed with input from subject matter experts and the established Network of Cancer Research Data Experts, ensures that training addresses real-world needs and can be easily updated to reflect emerging requirements. The guidance document for learning paths, produced collaboratively with this network, provides a replicable framework for constructing effective, outcome-oriented training programs.

The project also succeeded in launching and sustaining the Network of Cancer Research Data Experts, a European support network that brings together data stewards and professionals from research infrastructures, national initiatives, and competency centers. This network not only contributed directly to the project's outputs but is positioned to support ongoing and future initiatives, ensuring the long-term impact and sustainability of WP5's achievements. The network has actively participated in skills needs assessments, resource collation, and the development of the RDMkit Cancer View, and has been presented at major community events, such as the ELIXIR Cancer Data Community meeting and the EOSC Expert Group on Skills, Engagement and Adoption.

In summary, EOSC4Cancer has delivered a scalable, sustainable model for training and capacity building in cancer data research, acting as a key demonstrator in Skills4EOSC as a domain specific pilot, demonstrating best practices for the development of skills infrastructures in the EOSC, and putting into place connections to the work that will take place in future projects like CANDLE. These efforts contribute directly to the operational objectives of strengthening skills and training, supporting the uptake and effective use of EOSC services, and advancing the Action Area of skills and training. All planned activities were completed without deviation, and the outputs are well-positioned for continued use and further development in future European cancer research and data initiatives.

B. Key contributions subject to wider dissemination by the European Commission. Describe in more details the key contributions of your project *which you judge ready for wider dissemination* amongst the EOSC community. Typical examples include inspiring EOSC use cases, guidelines, toolkits, services, policies and good practices supporting any of the 3 EOSC Strategic Objectives. For each reported use case, please indicate to which of the following categories it best relates to:

- a. Assessment (eg incentives/rewards for researchers to practise open science¹)
- b. Data (eg research data management and research data that are open and/or follow the FAIR principles)
- c. Engagement (eg research that engages and involves citizens via citizen science)
- d. Infrastructure (eg data repositories, data stewardship, preservation of research outputs)
- e. Publications (eg research publications that are available in open access, licencing of publications, retention of IPR for publications)
- f. Services (ie services that enable research output discovery and exploitation, e.g. services for the execution of research workloads and code or for the visualisation, analysis, and sharing of research data)
- g. Skills/training (skills and training for researchers to practise open science)
- h. Software (eg open source software)

Roadmap to Build a Cancer Data Space (Assessment, Infrastructure, Data, Services)

The EOSC4Cancer Roadmap provides a strategic framework for establishing a federated, interoperable environment for cancer research data across Europe. This roadmap outlines the necessary steps, technical requirements, and policy recommendations to create a secure and FAIR-compliant data space, facilitating seamless data sharing, integration, and reuse among researchers, clinicians, and healthcare providers. By addressing infrastructure and data management challenges, this resource serves as a blueprint for national and international stakeholders aiming to accelerate cancer research through improved data stewardship and collaboration. Its dissemination will inspire similar initiatives in other domains and support the broader EOSC objective of enabling open and collaborative science.

¹ See also <https://coara.eu/>

Training Material on Services for Cancer Research (Skills/training)

EOSC4Cancer has developed comprehensive training materials focused on the effective use of EOSC-enabled tools and services for cancer research. This training portfolio is tailored to the evolving skill needs of researchers, biomedical professionals, and healthcare data specialists. By scaling training activities through a European support network, these resources address the critical need for interoperability and capacity building in cancer data research. The materials are designed for both self-learning and trainer-led sessions, supporting the EOSC strategic objective of strengthening research skills and fostering a culture of open science.

cBioPortal as a Hub of Cancer Research (Data, Software, Services, Infrastructure)

The integration of cBioPortal as a central hub within the cancer research data ecosystem exemplifies how open-source platforms can drive data visualization, analysis, and sharing. cBioPortal enables researchers to explore multidimensional cancer genomics data, facilitating hypothesis generation and collaborative discovery. Its deployment within the EOSC4Cancer framework demonstrates best practices in service integration, user engagement, and interoperability, making it a model use case for the EOSC community. Wider dissemination of this approach will encourage the adoption of robust, community-driven software solutions across other research domains.

Recommendations on Data Modelling and Ontology Use for Cancer Research (Data)

EOSC4Cancer's recommendations on data modelling and ontology selection provide actionable guidelines and best practices for structuring cancer research data. By advocating for the adoption of standardized ontologies and reporting frameworks, these recommendations promote data interoperability, discoverability, and reuse in line with FAIR principles. The guidelines are relevant not only for cancer researchers but also for data stewards and software developers, supporting consistent data annotation and integration across projects. Disseminating these recommendations will enhance data quality and facilitate cross-study analyses within the EOSC ecosystem. These recommendations are detailed in Deliverable D2.1 SOPs: Recommendations on Data Modelling and Ontology Use for Cancer Research, which consolidates insights from EOSC4Cancer use cases and aligns with existing international standards.

Virtual Research Environments to Facilitate the Analysis of Cancer Research Data (Services, Infrastructure, Software)

The deployment of Virtual Research Environments (VREs) tailored for cancer research exemplifies how computational platforms can streamline data analysis, workflow execution, and collaborative research. These VREs provide secure, scalable, and user-friendly workspaces where researchers can access datasets, run computational tools, and visualize results without local infrastructure constraints. Demonstrators developed within EOSC4Cancer, including the integration of data archives and cBioPortal with analysis platforms like openVRE and Galaxy, showcase the interconnection between VREs and specialized tools, enabling seamless access to and processing of multimodal cancer data. By demonstrating the practical benefits of VREs in cancer research, EOSC4Cancer contributes a replicable model for service delivery and infrastructure enhancement within EOSC, supporting both the technical and collaborative needs of the research community.

- C. Synergies with other stakeholders. If policy relevant, please describe the interactions and synergies of your project with other EOSC stakeholders (e.g. the EOSC-Association, other EU-funded projects, national authorities, research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures or others), with related international initiatives or with the communities involved in the development of the other data spaces of the European data strategy?

The EOSC-Life project, which creates a foundation data space with the 13 LS RIs in EOSC, is used as a reference within the EOSC4Cancer project: technical work packages follow its guidelines and practices to facilitate access to cancer data and facilities. EOSC4Cancer will build on data catalogues, workflow and tool systems, ensuring software good practices and provenance (e.g., using RO-CRATE), under FAIR guidance and AAI and computational capabilities provided by EOSC-Life WP7, which also deals with costs modeling.

In EOSC4Cancer, we have provided demonstrators that simulate the use of real sensitive data by employing synthetic datasets stored in real-world archival systems, accurately replicating the data flow and infrastructure setup needed for actual sensitive data use; these demonstrators also contribute input to the EuroScienceGateway project as part of a sensitive data use case.

Interestingly, there is a strong conceptual alignment with the BY-COVID project as both projects aim to enhance researchers capabilities to perform their scientific activities through exemplar use-cases in infectious diseases (BY-COVID) and cancer research (EOSC4Cancer), respectively. To be able to answer use-cases requirements, both projects count with dedicated efforts on analysis and interpretation platforms, data interoperability activities and data sources description, discovery and mobilization.

HealthyCloud was a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project aiming to generate a strategic agenda for the future Health Research and Innovation Cloud (HRIC) for the secondary use of health data across Europe. Recommendations, best practices and other outputs generated in the context of HealthyCloud have been taken by EOSC4Cancer and will contribute towards the project's long-term sustainability and its adoption by the coming projects in the context of EOSC and the EHDS. At the same time, such contributions will contribute to bringing EOSC and EHDS together for the development of the HRIC.

The stakeholder classification, reported as part of the Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science by the EOSC Executive Board, was used for the stakeholder engagement, communication and engagement methodology in EOSC4Cancer. It is also used as part of the EOSC4Cancer work package (WP5) to stratify the skills and training needs for the EOSC stakeholders in EOSC4Cancer.

EOSC4Cancer participated in the 2023 and 2024 EOSC Symposia. In 2023, coordinator Salvador Capella-Gutierrez presented in the session "EOSC contribution to the EU Missions", joined by representatives from BY-COVID, BlueCloud and FNS Cloud. The stakeholder forum created by EOSC4Cancer includes stakeholders of EOSC Association and EOSC projects. It conducted a dedicated Cancer Landscape Partnering Meeting with health-data focussed EOSC projects, featuring RAISE and SciLake. Key outcomes highlighted that health data needs special data protection within EOSC and that the upcoming EOSC governance structure should explore synergies with the EHDS and cancer research infrastructures. Finally, EOSC4Cancer contributes actively in the Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement Group and in the EOSC Forum through WP6 - among others with a dedicated communication campaign highlighting EOSC family projects.

EOSC4Cancer strongly aligned with 4.UNCAN.eu (CSA) and is ensuring a smooth handover with UNCAN CONNECT, which will implement a large-scale federated platform for cancer research. EOSC4Cancer will contribute insights on building technical infrastructures, working with use cases and linking to the European Health Data Space (EHDS). We are also aligning with other major cancer-related initiatives such as CANDLE, and EU-CIP to ensure that the outcomes of EOSC4Cancer are continued, adopted, and built upon by these new efforts. This includes insights on patient engagement and on dynamics of national vs. EU level implementation. Altogether, these alignment efforts will translate into recommendations for the European Cancer Mission and Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and will build a reasonable basis of protocols and technical developments for future projects.

EOSC4Cancer also pioneered synergies with the main projects implementing EHDS for secondary use: TEHDAS2 and HealthData@EU pilot. Notably, we conducted a joint workshop with TEHDAS2 30 January 2025 in Warsaw, exploring the relationship between EHDS secondary and cancer data. The workshop highlighted pioneer work from cancer research that can inspire EHDS construction - e.g. high-quality data, structured data collection and prior experience with data sharing initiatives. It pointed out TEHDAS2's contributions towards bridging the gap between these cancer research practices and the EHDS - via guidelines, metadata catalogue, stakeholder collaboration models and interpretation of EHDS legal requirements.

The on-going HealthData@EU pilot has a use case on cancer genomics. EOSC4Cancer has continuously exchanged on this use case - jointly with GDI and via shared consortium partners.

The CanSERV project aimed to provide different data types produced in diverse scenarios, which complement the possibilities of data generation efforts by illustrating the benefits of generating research data for advancing cancer research.

- D. EOSC challenges and lessons learnt of a policy nature. Please briefly describe the main challenges that your project encountered regarding technical development, cooperation, support, dissemination and/or exploitation of the project's deliverables into the EOSC context. Do you have policy recommendations to help addressing these challenges?

EOSC4Cancer tackles a very specific topic: health-related research, specifically in the context of cancer. Similarities with other projects exist with BY-COVID as the main example, although it focuses on a different type of diseases. SciLake has a use case related to cancer, although the project is not health specific. RAISE has a pilot on health, but not covering cancer. So, none of them are approaching cancer research from the EOSC4Cancer point of view. Thus, the challenge that we faced is that the people within the EOSC Landscape did not have specific knowledge about cancer research and this needs to be taken into account when communicating our contributions, for example, during EOSC Symposium and other EOSC related activities.

To address this challenge, the EOSC Association could ensure that the dissemination levels (i.e., domain specific, general audience, etc.) and in accordance with the delivered messages to the EOSC community. It could also provide sessions that are domain specific, so the level of understanding of the audience would be greater and the presentations could be more focused on the real challenges, rather than having to adhere to a general and high level overview. In this domain, it should also leverage the work of its Health Data Task Force - especially from Key Focus Area 4 on partnership between EOSC and EHDS communities. Focussing on cross-cutting topics like the EU missions (as in Symposium 2023) also provides angles under which health-data projects can be disseminated in a way that is interesting to broader EOSC audiences.

- E. Link to other EU policy priorities (beyond EOSC). Is your project contributing to advance other policy priorities of the EU (e.g. Horizon Europe Missions, Sustainable Development Goals, EU sectoral policies or others)? In case of positive reply, please list those EU policy priorities and explain briefly the nature of the project's contributions.

The objective of EOSC4Cancer is to provide protocols, best practices, reference implementations and access to research software, including analytical workflows, for accelerating and standardising cancer-related research in the context of the European Cancer Mission. To make that possible, EOSC4Cancer is based on different use-cases that serve as examples of the Cancer Patient Journey. Thus, It will contribute to developing plans for the Cancer Data Space with the ultimate goal of informing the EU Cancer Mission. EOSC4Cancer has been closely collaborating with UNCAN.eu to achieve the integration of existing research infrastructures, e.g. ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, EuroBioimaging; relevant initiatives and projects like 1+MG, B1MG, GDI, EUCAIM, CanSERV, and cancer data infrastructures. It will ensure that the cancer use-case is covered by the maturity models currently being developed by B1MG, ELIXIR-CONVERGE, GA4GH, and other projects. Bringing together those efforts would facilitate incorporating different perspectives, scenarios and aspects for organisations seeking to share responsibly sensitive human data for research purposes. The results of the EOSC4Cancer use-case implementations will cover the Cancer Patient Journey, from prevention and early diagnosis to treatments in advanced stages of the disease. These outputs, in form of guidelines and recommendations, will serve as guides for the development of the EU Cancer Mission portfolio.

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) is a policy-framing and technical standard-setting organisation that aims to enable responsible genomic data sharing within a human rights framework. Their standards and guidelines have been adopted throughout the project and incorporated in the technical developments of the EOSC4Cancer Consortium, which will be assured by the contribution of project participants to the GA4GH.

The European Health Data Space is a major policy priority that EOSC4Cancer has continuously contributed to (section C for details). Main contributions to link cancer research to the EHDS include stakeholder alignment, initial comparative analysis of respective timelines and infrastructures, highlight

of low-hanging fruits of cancer research that EHDS can benefit from and role of central EHDS projects, like TEHDAS2 and HealthData@EU.

EOSC4Cancer is actively aligning its outcomes and roadmap with key projects funded under the EU Cancer Mission, including UNCAN-Connect, CANDLE, and EU-CIP. Aiming to contribute to a federated infrastructure for cancer research in Europe, EOSC4Cancer is engaging with these projects to ensure continuity, reuse, and long-term sustainability of its results. This alignment is a core element of the EOSC4Cancer sustainability roadmap, ensuring that its data models, tools, and recommendations are integrated into and adopted by these flagship Cancer Mission platforms.

Overall, EOSC4Cancer is working to serve cancer researchers, and ultimately cancer patients, by facilitating data access from cancer networks and European research infrastructures, using open data standards (taking GA4GH and ICGC as references in the field of cancer), building on and further collaborating with the EOSC ecosystem, synergizing with stakeholders like I+MG/B1MG and EUCAIM, and contributing towards the European Health Data Space and the European Cancer Mission.

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY (MAX 1P)

This section should be filled only by projects in their final reporting period.

Indicate how the main project's outputs could be further maintained, supported and integrated in the broader EOSC federation after the end date of the project.

To ensure the long-term sustainability and impact of EOSC4Cancer, the project has developed a dedicated sustainability plan that outlines how its key outputs, such as data models, tools and workflows, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and guidelines and interconnection of virtual research environments (VREs), can be maintained, adopted, and integrated beyond the project's end.

All project developments have been aligned with existing EOSC services and European Research Infrastructures (RIs) such as ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, and Euro-BioImaging, ensuring technical and strategic interoperability. These RIs have supported the co-design of services and will play a key role in sustaining EOSC4Cancer outputs after the project ends, contributing operational capacity, standards alignment, and community engagement.

Additionally, EOSC4Cancer is actively aligning with flagship initiatives of the EU Cancer Mission, including UNCAN.eu / UNCAN-Connect, CANDLE, and EU-CIP, projects funded under Horizon Europe and focused on advancing European cancer research. This alignment aims to ensure that EOSC4Cancer results are adopted, extended, and sustained through these future initiatives. Key developments, such as SOPs, recommendations, data models, enhanced VREs, and data access frameworks, are being shared with these projects to guarantee continuity and avoid duplication of effort.

Importantly, EOSC4Cancer builds upon prior work from EOSC-related and cancer data projects and, in turn, establishes a foundation for upcoming initiatives. The project's commitment to open science, FAIR principles, and shared community standards ensures that its assets will remain accessible, usable, and relevant beyond the project's lifetime, continuing to support cancer research and data-driven innovation in the years ahead.